

Collection of Social Anxiety Disorder (SAD) related Information Needs clustered in thematic categories

* Information needs mentioned more than once may differ slightly in language but are identical in content. All information needs are classified equally for the analysis, i.e., both information needs to be mentioned more than once, and information needs only mentioned by one participant. All mentioned information needs were clustered and then translated from German into English for publication.

Thematic category of information need	Total mentions of information needs per category	Information needs	Mentions	Participant ID
Diagnosis and symptoms	30	What is social anxiety/phobia?	5	SP05, SP06, SP10, SP16, SP08
		What do social anxiety symptoms look like? What does a social anxiety diagnosis look like?	4	SP16, SP19, SP20, SP12
		Are my anxieties normal/abnormal?	4	SP10, SP12, SP03, SP04
		Researching concrete symptoms: fear of people	2	SP12, SP08
		What is part of social anxiety, and what is not?	2	SP09, SP10
		Where does social anxiety start?	1	SP08
		Is social anxiety something physical?	1	SP12
		Does an illness even exist to the symptoms I have?	1	SP12
		Is extreme shyness as a clinical picture?	1	SP05
		Researching social anxiety self-tests (on the internet)	1	SP08
		Researching concrete symptoms: muscle twitching/extreme physical tension/types of vertigo	1	SP20
		Researching concrete symptoms: do brain zaps exist?	1	SP20
		Researching concrete symptoms: why do I have sweaty palms?	1	SP20
		Am I just introverted, or do I have social anxiety?	1	SP18
		Is my behavior a symptom of a mental disorder or simply my personality?	1	SP08
		What do concrete psychological terms mean?	1	SP08
		How many people are affected/diagnosed by social anxiety disorder?	1	SP08
Is it part of the clinical picture that I think I have no friends?	1	SP06		
Intrapersonal, self-discovery, and self-awareness	25	Is it just me, or is it my disorder or just my personality?	2	SP08, SP18
		Personal questions and self-reflection in connection with my social anxiety	3	SP11, SP08, SP04
		Am I acting strangely?	1	SP03
		Am I okay the way I am? Am I allowed to be as I am?	1	SP04
		Do I really feel bad or does everyone else feel the same way?	1	SP16
		Am I really suffering?	1	SP16
		Should I change something or should I accept it as it is?	1	SP16
		What is wrong with me?	1	SP16
		What am I doing wrong?	1	SP16
		How do I get out of it?	1	SP16
		Will it get better for me at some point?	1	SP16
		How much of what I perceive is real?	1	SP16
		Who am I, and why am I the way I am?	1	SP03
		How can I live better, or how can I be better?	1	SP03
		What is going on with me?	1	SP04
		Where does my social anxiety come from? (personal experiences/trauma: e.g., disappointed expectations from parents)	1	SP07
		What exactly was the trigger for my social anxiety?	1	SP18
How can I be self-confident?	1	SP20		
How can I understand myself better?	1	SP04		
What is behind the anxiety?	1	SP05		
What causes my anxiety?	1	SP05		
What do I do with myself if I have social anxiety?	1	SP10		
Therapy, treatment, and recovery	21	Will my social anxiety go away? How does it go away?	3	SP05, SP12, SP10
		How do I get a place in therapy / clinic?	2	SP05, SP08
		What can I do to cure my social anxiety?	2	SP16, SP18
		Forms of therapy / treatment options: Rehabilitation clinics? Core Energetic [body therapy]?	2	SP16, SP19
		How long will it take to get better? / How much time does it take?	2	SP06, SP18
		What are the chances of treatment / cure?	1	SP05
		How much does my condition have to do with social media consumption? Can I regulate my condition when I consume social media less?	1	SP06
		Can therapy help me? What type of therapy can help me?	1	SP14
		Depth psychology-based psychotherapy, or behavioral therapy?	1	SP14
		What are the benefits of depth psychology-based psychotherapy?	1	SP14
		Can physical symptoms go away again?	1	SP22
		Depression and social anxiety disorder? Where do you start therapy with two diagnoses?	1	SP12
		Why is nothing being found that helps?	1	SP09
What forms of therapy are there? What exactly is done there, i.e., methodology	1	SP08		
Physical symptoms: What can be done about / against them?	1	SP22		
Support	18	Where can I find support groups? What kind of support groups are there?	6	SP05, SP4, SP16, SP23, SP14, SP24
		Where / how can I find a psychotherapist?	3	SP16, SP24, SP08
		Where can I get help? What options are there for help?	2	SP04, SP12
		Can friends help me?	1	SP06
		Are there counseling centers for social anxiety? Does a counseling center refer me to a psychotherapist?	1	SP10
		Are there self-help groups I can attend at my university?	1	SP14
		Can support groups help me? In what way?	1	SP14
		What contact and counseling centers are there in my area? What do they offer?	1	SP24
		Where is a counseling center? Can I just call them?	1	SP06
Where can I find a psychiatrist?	1	SP14		
Well-being and health practices	17	How can I get rid of panic attacks/anxiety attacks?	2	SP05, SP19
		What can I do to reduce anxiety? Which possibilities for tips exist?	2	SP09, SP12
		How can I live better?	1	SP04
		Skills lists against extreme tension	1	SP05
		Instructions on meditation/relaxation on YouTube	1	SP06
		What can I do to keep my anxiety from interfering with my daily life?	1	SP09
		What can I do to even maybe get rid of social anxiety disorder?	1	SP09
		How do I find methods that help?	1	SP09
		Tips against problems with falling asleep and social anxiety	1	SP11
		What can do against muscle twitching? (extreme physical tension)	1	SP11
		What could I do apart from therapy that would make me feel better in my situation?	1	SP14
		Where can I find an MBSR course? (Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction)	1	SP15
How can I focus and how I design my life to make everything work in a sustainable way?	1	SP19		

		How can I learn to leave the house?	1	SP03
		What methods are there that I can use acutely?	1	SP06
Community	15	Are there tips/experiences from other affected people? (<i>Questions mentioned in combination with the main Information Need for exemplification: What helps other affected people? How are other affected people coping with the SAD? Where do they have problems/where do problems overlap? Which symptoms do other affected have?</i>)	12	SP12, SP14, SP11, SP13, SP05, SP16, SP09, SP14, SP06, SP03, SP08, SP10
		Who else has social anxiety besides me has SAD and can I find other affected people on Instagram?	2	SP10, SP05
		Where can I find reports of other affected individuals' experiences?	1	SP08
Stigmatization and external perception	15	Will I be accepted, laughed at/understood?	2	SP12, SP18
		How am I viewed from the outside? How does this affect others? How do others see me?	2	SP03, SP06
		Do other people notice that I have SAD? (e.g., from how I behave)	2	SP03, SP06
		Is there anyone who knows anything about my diagnosis?	2	SP10, SP12
		Why are psychological issues still stigmatized?	1	SP09
		Do I act or behave strangely? (Asking others for feedback)	1	SP03
		Can I talk to someone about my illness? Who can I talk to about my illness?	1	SP03
		What is appropriate/inappropriate to communicate about my illness?	1	SP03
		Am I okay the way I am? (Asking others for feedback/confirmation)	1	SP04
		Do I seem as weird to people as I feel?	1	SP06
		Are other students from my university are also affected and to afraid to speak up about it?	1	SP14
Work, education, and study	14	How does a work a disadvantage compensation at university work?	1	SP05
		How do I submit an application?	1	SP05
		Would it help me if colleagues and my boss knew about my illness?	1	SP06
		What would be the best strategy to deal with social anxiety at work?	1	SP06
		How can a social anxiety condition be integrated with work?	1	SP06
		Working with people and stress	1	SP12
		How do I make my money with this condition?	1	SP19
		What kind of work can I do with this condition? Where can I find home office jobs?	1	SP19
		Can I reveal my condition at work? Who do I tell?	1	SP03
		Will anything change if I speak about my condition at work?	1	SP03
		Would my boss/colleagues be more considerate about workload if they knew about my condition?	1	SP06
		How can you live with Social Anxiety in your day-to-day job?	1	SP06
		How smart is it to tell your supervisor or colleagues? Who should know? Who should not know?	1	SP06
		Do I get burnout when I work with Social Anxiety or can I work with the condition at all?	1	SP12
Comorbid mental disorders	12	What specifically are the symptoms of social anxiety, and are other emotions that I am feeling also part of SAD or an other mental disorder?	3	SP14, SP04, SP12
		Researching ADHD / ADD and social anxiety, e.g., do I have also ADHD / ADD?	2	SP14, SP01
		What is social anxiety, and what is depression? How closely related are my depression and my social anxiety?	2	SP06, SP12
		Researching Autism and social anxiety, e.g. is social anxiety related to autism?	1	SP12
		What is Agoraphobia?	1	SP04
		What is borderline personality disorder? What does it consist of? How does it show itself?	1	SP24
		Researching paranoid schizophrenia	1	SP13
		What are the different types of (comorbid) disorders?	1	SP19
Social	9	How does social phobia affect or compromise friendships?	1	SP06
		Is this my illness, that I think I have no friends?	1	SP06
		Researching about belonging and distancing of relatives	1	SP07
		Researching isolation	1	SP07
		Would anyone understand me? (Searching for friends)	1	SP12
		How can I make new contacts/friends?	1	SP20
		Do social apps help to keep in touch with my family?	1	SP23
		How can people with depression or anxiety disorders date?	1	SP01
		Can friends help me with social anxiety? Would it help if my friends knew that I have social anxiety?	1	SP06
(Digital) media	9	Where can I find books on social anxiety?	2	SP14, SP20
		Where can I find podcasts on social anxiety?	1	SP14
		Where can I find information on social anxiety on the internet?	1	SP15
		What apps can help me keep in touch with my family?	1	SP23
		Which books can help me?	1	SP23
		Where can I find software on social anxiety?	1	SP01
		Where can I find factual information on how to find help for SAD?	1	SP11
		How can I find good instructions for SAD meditation/relaxation on YouTube?	1	SP06
Mental health concerns	7	What is the reason behind anxiety? How does anxiety originate?	2	SP05, SP06
		Why is assisted suicide not permitted in Germany for mental illnesses?	1	SP09
		How much does social anxiety have to do with social media consumption?	1	SP06
		Search for information on cross-general anxiety/inherited anxieties	1	SP07
		How do emotions/thoughts develop?	1	SP20
		Research on disturbance patterns of other diseases of which I am not affected	1	SP19
Day structuring and organization	4	How can I plan my purchases?	1	SP02
		How can I learn to leave the house?	1	SP04
		How do I create a balance between flow and structure in my everyday life?	1	SP19
		Is there helpful software that can be used somehow to better structure myself and my everyday life?	1	SP01
Emergency	4	What can I do in case of emergency?	1	SP06
		What is the crisis service number and what kind of support is there when I am in distress?	1	SP24
		Research on suicide	1	SP09
		Research on assisted suicide	1	SP09
Medical	3	What medications are available for my condition?	1	SP20
		Medical interventions against anxieties and erotophobia	1	SP20
		Are there medications that can help with sweating?	1	SP22

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